

STRENGTH PREDICTION OF IMPACT DAMAGED COMPOSITES - AN ENGINEERING MODEL -

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ABSTRACT

A simple method for predicting the uniaxial compression strength of laminated composites containing impact damages is presented. The method is based on a simplified model of the damage zone and a fracture criterion originally developed for notched laminates. This approach allows to derive a closed-form equation expressing the post-impact strength as a function of the damage size and damage intensity. The properties of the damaged laminate are characterized by two parameters which have to be determined from experimental data. Some examples are given showing that the predicted strength is in good agreement with test results.

Keywords: composite material, compression-after-impact, impact damage, damage tolerance

1. INTRODUCTION

Damages resulting from low velocity impacts of blunt objects (debris, dropped tools etc.) may strongly affect the static strength of structural components made of composites. This is true especially for compression loaded laminates. As load bearing composite structures used for aerospace applications (airplane and helicopter airframes, rotor blades) have to meet damage tolerance requirements the behaviour of damaged components has to be considered already in the design process. For this task simple analytical tools are required which should be capable to predict the failure strength of damaged composites with sufficient accuracy.

Several analytical methods for predicting the strength of impact damaged laminated composites have been proposed ranging from comprehensive numerical methods to simplified semi-empirical fracture models. The most frequently used numerical technique is the finite element method combined with energy based fracture criteria (e.g. [1]). Though being a very powerful and flexible tool numerical simulation is often too time consuming and expensive for practical design applications. Also, the modelling of the complex damage state resulting from high energy impacts (combination of several micro- and macro-mechanics failure modes; see Figure 1) raise problems. Semi-empirical methods overcome this problem by using simplified models of the damaged region. In [2] it was proposed to replace the damage zone by a hole [2], and in [3] an equivalent delamination was introduced. The first approach tends to overestimate the effect of small damages, whereas the delamination approach is only applicable to low impact energy levels that result mostly in delaminations.

In this paper an analytical model is proposed which combines simplicity with the capability to consider impact damages ranging from small delaminations caused by low energy impacts to through-penetration (Figure 1). This method is, therefore, well suited for design tasks such as structural optimization. Details of the approach are given in the following.

2. ANALYTICAL MODEL

2.1. Basic philosophy

The developed model is based on the fact that local defects (broken fibres, delaminated plies) caused by a foreign object impact result in a stiffness degradation of the damaged laminate region. The extent of the stiffness reduction depends on the type and density of the local defects. In a loaded laminate the discontinuous stiffness distribution induces stress concentrations at the edge of the damage zone (see Figure 2). The basic idea of the present approach now is to assume that the residual strength of an impact damaged laminate is a function of the stress concentrations in the undamaged material surrounding the damage zone. Similar models have been successfully applied to predict the tensile strength of notched laminates [4].

In order to derive a simple analytical model the damage zone, which has an inhomogeneous and very complex structure in reality, is approximated by a homogeneous elastic inclusion of the same maximum size as shown in Figure 2. The reduced in-plane stiffness of the inclusion is obtained by scaling the stiffness properties of the undamaged laminate. The scaling factor characterizes the damage intensity. This simplified model of the damage zone allows to determine the stress field in the laminate analytically using solutions based on the elasticity theory of anisotropic plates [5]. The strength of the damaged laminate is obtained by applying stress field based composite failure criteria. Both the stiffness reduction factor as well as the parameters of the failure criterion are material dependent. They take into account the influence of variables such as fibre/matrix properties, laminate configuration, damage types etc., and have to be determined experimentally.

2.2. Stress distribution

In case of an uniaxial compression loaded orthotropic laminate an explicit expression for the stress distribution normal to the load direction can be derived provided that the damaged region can be approximated by a circular area. The resulting equation is based on the approximation given by Konish and Whitney [6] for the net section stress distribution of an infinite plate containing an open circular hole of radius R . For a laminate loaded by a uniform stress σ_y^∞ applied parallel to the y -axis the stress distribution along the x -axis can be approximated by

$$\sigma_y(x, 0) = \frac{\sigma_y^\infty}{2} \left[2 + \left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^2 + 3\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^4 - (K_T^\infty - 3) \left\{ 5\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^6 - 7\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^8 \right\} \right], \quad (1)$$

where K_T^∞ is the orthotropic stress concentration factor [6]. In order to take into account the effect of a circular elastic inclusion the approximation given by Equation (1) is scaled by the ratio of the open hole to the elastic core stress concentration $K_D = K_{T, core}^\infty / K_{T, hole}^\infty$ resulting in following expression:

$$\sigma_y(x, 0) = \sigma_y^\infty \{ 1 + K_D F(x) \} \quad (2)$$

where

$$F(x) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^2 + 3\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^4 - (K_T - 3) \left\{ 5\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^6 - 7\left(\frac{R}{x}\right)^8 \right\} \right].$$

The ratio K_D is a function of the inclusion stiffness. In the fracture model it will be used as the parameter characterizing the damage intensity. For $K_D = 0$ the stress distribution of an undamaged laminate is obtained whereas for $K_D = 1$ the open hole solution Equation (1) is recovered.

In Figure 3 net section stress distributions obtained from the exact solution provided by Lekhnitskii [5] and Equation (2) are compared. Three different K_D values are investigated. The curves resulting from both solution methods show a very good agreement. Hence it follows that Equation (2) is a suitable approximate solution for the stress distribution adjacent to an elastic core in an uniaxial loaded infinite orthotropic laminated plate.

2.3. Failure Criterion

Several failure criteria based on stress fields are available which were developed to predict the failure of notched laminates [4]. In order to keep the number of parameters low the point stress criterion of Nuismer and Whitney [7] is chosen. This one parameter criterion assumes failure to occur when the stress at some fixed distance a_0 ahead from a discontinuity causing the stress concentration reaches the strength σ_0 of the unnotched laminate:

$$\sigma_y(x = R + a_0, 0) = \sigma_0. \quad (3)$$

Using this criterion with Equation (2) results in the normalized residual strength of the damaged infinite laminated plate:

$$\frac{\sigma_D^\infty}{\sigma_0} = \frac{1}{1 + K_D F(x = R + a_0)}. \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) represents a two parameter fracture model, where K_D characterizes type and intensity of the damage and a_0 the notch sensitivity of the material. Both are depending on the laminate configuration and have to be determined experimentally.

So far it has been assumed that the damaged plates are of infinite width. In order to apply the model to real life problems a finite width correction factor Y has to be introduced. The strength of a damaged plate of finite width then reads:

$$\frac{\sigma_D}{\sigma_0} = \frac{1}{Y} \frac{\sigma_D^\infty}{\sigma_0}. \quad (5)$$

No closed-form solution of this problem is available for the case of an orthotropic plate containing an elastic core. Therefore, the closed-form expression valid for plates with open holes will be used. This approach seems feasible as the net section stress distribution which forms the basis of Equation (2) is also derived from the open hole problem. The approximate expression for an open hole is given by the relation [7]:

$$Y = \frac{2 + (1 - 2R/W)^3}{3(1 - 2R/W)}, \quad (6)$$

where W is the finite width of the plate. Relation (6) should not be used in case the damage size approaches the plate width, because the strength decreases to zero for $2R/W \rightarrow 1$. This limit is true for open holes but not for impacted laminates which still have a residual strength in case the whole width is damaged.

2.4. Calibration

As mentioned before, the fracture model has to be calibrated by utilizing experimental strength data. The proposed model provides only two parameters to take into account the influence of various variables such as material properties, laminate stacking sequence, damage type, and damage severity. Consequently, both model parameters have to be determined for each combination of variables effecting the residual strength, at least for each material system and laminate configuration.

Each set of K_D and α_0 should be determined from compression-after-impact strength data obtained from a batch of laminated plates differing only in the size of the inflicted damage. The usual procedure applied to produce different damage sizes is to impact the laminates by a single impactor at several energy levels. The result is that damage diameter and damage intensity are no independent variables. For example, a high energy impact results not only in a larger damage size, but also causes more severe local defects compared to a low energy impact. This interdependence has to be considered in Equation (4). It is assumed that the damage severity increase follows an exponential law:

$$K_D = \hat{K}_D \left[1 - \exp \left\{ -(\hat{c}R)^2 \right\} \right], \quad (7)$$

where \hat{K}_D characterizes the maximum damage severity obtained for the examined laminate (e.g. through-penetration for thin laminates) and \hat{c} the corresponding damage size.

Both K_D and α_0 have to be calculated simultaneously applying error minimization techniques. In the present approach the least square method is used to minimize the difference between the strength degradation curve expressed by Equation (4) and the experimental strength data.

3. EXAMPLES

In order to demonstrate the ability of the developed model to predict the strength reduction as a function of the damage size some examples are given in the following. The data needed for model calibration have been taken from open literature as well as from own experimental work. In all cases the Boeing compression-after-impact test procedure [8] was used to determine the strength data. The damage width was obtained from ultrasonic C-scanning.

The first example deals with the strength degradation behaviour of quasi-isotropic laminates impacted at different energy levels. Experimental data published by Ilcewicz et al. [9] were used for model calibration. The test specimens were made of IM 7 carbon fibres and a tough epoxy resin (8551-7), and had overall in-plane dimensions of 152mm x 102mm and a thickness of 3mm. To get the residual strength of equivalent infinite plates the finite width correction procedure given in Section 2.3. was applied. The model parameters K_D and α_0 were determined using an error minimization procedure based on the least square method. Figure 4 shows that the curve resulting from Equation (4) gives a very good approximation of the strength degradation observed in the experiment. The determined point stress distance $\alpha_0 = 1.35\text{mm}$ is comparable to values which are typical for laminates containing open holes.

The same model parameters were used to predict the compressive strength of impacted quasi-isotropic plates made of different CFRP materials including standard as well as toughened thermosets. The experimental data were taken from reference [10]. All test specimens were impacted at an energy of 3.3J/mm. The overall dimensions of the tested plates differ from that used in [9] only by a slightly larger laminate thickness (4mm). The predicted residual strength curve and the test results are compared in Figure 5 revealing a very good agreement. From that it can be concluded that the characteristic parameters of the model are not very sensitive to the type of material and to small thickness variations. This seems to be true at least for monolithic graphite/epoxy laminates.

The last example demonstrates the ability of the model to deal with finite width effects. Two types of sandwich plates differing only in in-plane dimensions were both experimentally and analytically examined. The test specimens had 12mm Nomex cores and [0/90, ±45, 0/90, ±45, 0/90] lay-up face-sheets made of graphite/epoxy fabric material. All specimens were damaged by a hemispherical steel impactor of 25mm diameter. The larger type "A" specimens had in-plane dimensions of 100mm x 150mm, whereas the type "B" specimens were only 50mm long and 100mm high. The first step of the analytical approach was to calibrate the model using the experimental strength data of the type "A" specimens (see Figure 6). Then, the same characteristic parameters were used to predict the

compression strength of the smaller type "B" specimens. In Figure 6 the test results are compared to the calculated strength curves. For both specimen types a good correlation between experiment and analytical description can be observed.

4. Conclusions

A simple analytical technique to predict the compressive strength of impact damaged laminates as a function of the damage size was developed. The damage zone is modelled as a circular elastic inclusion with reduced stiffness. This approach allows to derive a closed-form expression for the stress distribution in the net section of the laminate. The point stress failure criterion is applied to this distribution resulting in a two-parameter fracture model. One parameter characterizes the damage intensity, the other the notch sensitivity of the laminate. Both have to be determined experimentally for each material system and laminate configuration independently.

Experimental strength data of several impact damaged monolithic laminates and sandwich face-sheets have been compared to strength degradation curves obtained from the proposed model showing a good agreement between prediction and test results. Also, the capability of the model to consider the size effect of finite laminates could be demonstrated. Some of the analysed experimental data taken from open literature revealed that the characteristic model parameters seem to be constant for a number of CFRP systems. However, this result still has to be verified by evaluating additional test data.

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Figure 1: Typical damages caused by foreign object impacts

Figure 2: Impact damage model

Figure 3: Normalized net section stress $\sigma_y(x, 0)/\sigma_y^\infty$ in a plate containing an elastic inclusion

Figure 4: Compression strength vs. damage width for quasi-isotropic CFRP specimens (from [9])

Figure 5: Compression strength versus damage width for quasi-isotropic specimens made of different CFRP materials (from [10])

Figure 6: Compression strength versus damage width for CFRP sandwich specimens of different size